

Systematic Review on Benzene, Toluene, Ethylbenzene, and Xylene (BTEX) Emissions, Health Impact Assessment, and Detection Techniques in Oil and Natural Gas Operations

Characteristics of studies

Characteristics of included studies

Akerstrom et al 2016

Methods	The study aimed to assess personal exposure to benzene and 1,3-butadiene at petroleum refineries during turnarounds and in the oil harbor. Full-shift personal exposure measurements were taken during refinery turnarounds and at the oil harbor. Measurements were taken during work tasks with higher assumed benzene exposure, using diffusive samplers. The study included refinery workers, contractors, sewage tanker drivers, jetty workers, and dockworkers. PerkinElmer diffusive samplers filled with Carbopack X were used for all exposure measurements. Chemical analysis was performed using a gas chromatograph. Questionnaires were used to collect data on tasks performed, time spent outdoors, and use of respiratory protective equipment. Weather conditions were also recorded.
Participants	The study included process technicians, contractors, turnaround coordinators, maintenance workers, process engineers, jetty workers, dockworkers, and sewage tanker drivers working at petroleum refineries and oil harbors.
Interventions	The intervention involved taking full-shift personal exposure measurements of benzene and 1,3-butadiene during work tasks with assumed higher benzene exposure.
Outcomes	The study found that workers in certain occupational groups, such as contractors, sewage tanker drivers, and oil harbor workers, had personal benzene exposures exceeding the Swedish occupational exposure limit (OEL). The exposure to 1,3-butadiene was very low and did not exceed the OEL.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	There is a low risk of detection bias, as exposure measurements were taken objectively using diffusive samplers and analyzed using validated methods.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	There is a low risk of attrition bias, as repeated measurements were conducted when available, and single measurements were taken due to organizational differences in some cases.

Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	There is a low risk of reporting bias, as the study methods and results are described in detail, including exposure levels and compliance with OELs.
Other bias	Low risk	The study design appears to be well-conducted, but there may be potential bias due to the selection of work tasks for measurement, which were determined a priori and may not represent all potential high-exposure scenarios in the refinery.

Alimohammadi et al 2023

Methods	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sampling Method: The study used the NIOSH 1501 method for sampling occupational exposure to BTEX compounds. This method involves using activated charcoal adsorbent tubes connected to personal sampling pumps worn by workers. 2. Sample Collection: Each participant's respiratory exposure was measured with three samples during a work shift: one at the beginning, one in the middle, and one at the end. A total of 180 samples were collected (30 workers x 3 samples x 2 seasons). 3. Environmental Samples: Environmental samples were also collected to determine BTEX concentrations in the restrooms of each station. Six environmental samples were collected (one sample per room). 4. Sample Preparation: After collection, both sides of the adsorbent tubes were protected with plastic caps and stored in a cool box. The activated charcoal from the tubes was transferred to vials for analysis. 5. Sample Analysis: The extracted analytes were analyzed using Gas Chromatography-Flame Ionization Detector (GC-FID). A calibration curve was plotted using standard solutions of benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylene. The area under the chromatographic peak was determined to quantify the amount of analytes.
Participants	The study included employees with at least 12 months of work experience, respiratory exposure to BTEX vapors, non-smoking, and sufficient consent to participate. A total of 30 workers (5 workers per station) were surveyed in two seasons (summer and winter) in six fuel distribution stations in Karaj.
Interventions	Occupational exposure to BTEX compounds was measured using the NIOSH 1501 method. Cancer and non-cancer risk assessments were performed according to the USEPA method.
Outcomes	The study aimed to assess the carcinogenic and health risks of occupational exposure to BTEX compounds in gasoline fuel distribution stations in Karaj.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
------	--------------------	-----------------------

Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	The study used standardized methods for measuring BTEX exposure and risk assessment, which reduces the risk of detection bias.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	There is no indication of attrition bias as all participants completed the study.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	The study appears to have reported all measured outcomes without selective reporting, reducing the risk of reporting bias.
Other bias	Low risk	The study's design and methods seem robust, but potential sources of bias could include confounding factors not accounted for in the analysis, such as individual differences in exposure levels or other environmental factors.

Bari et al 2018

Methods	Investigation of ambient levels and sources of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and associated public health risks in two northern Alberta oil sands communities.
Participants	The study focused on ambient air quality in two communities near oil sands development.
Interventions	Monitoring of VOC levels using stainless steel canisters over a 24-hour period at a 1-in-12 day frequency during 2010–2011 and every 6 days from 2012 onwards.
Outcomes	Measurement and analysis of total VOC levels, identification of predominant VOCs, comparison of hazardous VOC concentrations with regulatory health risk screening criteria, and source apportionment using the Positive Matrix Factorization (PMF) model.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	The study used standard methods for VOC measurement (USEPA Method TO-14 and TO-15) to minimize detection bias.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	The study period (January 2010–March 2015) was selected to avoid instrumental and/or laboratory bias associated with the analysis. However, the reported detection limit for some species deteriorated after April 2015, which could affect the interpretation of results.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	The study provided detailed information on methods, results, and conclusions, reducing the risk of reporting bias. However, the exclusion of some abundant VOC species from measurement may limit the comprehensiveness of the findings.

Other bias	Unclear risk	The study focused on two specific communities near oil sands development, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other regions. Additionally, the study did not consider potential confounding factors that could influence VOC levels and health risks.
------------	--------------	---

Chaiklieng et al 2019

Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sampling Site and Study Population: Conducted in Khon Kaen, Thailand, at 98 gasoline stations categorized into urban, suburban, and rural zones. Included 150 gasoline station workers (137 fueling workers, 13 cashiers). ● Measurement of Benzene Concentration: Personal sampling of ambient benzene concentration. ● Data Collection: Interviews and on-site observations to collect additional working characteristic data. ● Risk Assessment: Used the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) guidelines for risk assessment.
Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number: 150 gasoline station workers (137 fueling workers, 13 cashiers). ● Characteristics: Non-smokers, limited passive smoking exposure.
Interventions	Observational: No specific intervention, only assessment of benzene exposure and associated health risks.
Outcomes	<p>Health Risk Assessment: Adverse Health Effects: 51.33% of workers had Hazard Quotients (HQ) >1, indicating a high risk.</p> <p>Cancer Risk: Increased from 1.35×10^{-8} to 1.52×10^{-4}, with 70.67% of workers having a lifetime cancer risk above the Inhalation Unit Risk (IUR) of 2.2×10^{-6}.</p> <p>Comparison: Fueling workers had significantly higher risk than cashiers. Workers in inner-city zones had higher risk than rural zones.</p>
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	Low risk, as benzene concentration measurements were likely objective.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	Low risk, as all participants were included in the analysis.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	Low risk, as the study appears to report all relevant outcomes and findings.
Other bias	High risk	Potential bias in exposure assessment due to limited sampling time and single measurement assumption for the average shift length.

Chaiklieng et al 2021

Methods	The study aimed to assess the risk of exposure to benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylene (BTEX) compounds at gasoline stations, focusing on hazardous area classification and worker risk assessment.
Participants	The study included 47 gasoline stations in Khon Kaen province, Thailand. Workers at these stations were involved in the study.
Interventions	The study measured BTEX concentrations in ambient air using active sampling with charcoal tubes, following NIOSH method 1501. Flammability levels were measured using a flammable gas detector during vehicle refueling.
Outcomes	The study assessed the risk of worker exposure to BTEX using the hazard index (HI), calculated based on BTEX concentrations and the number of gasoline dispensers and daily gasoline sold. Hazardous areas were classified based on BTEX concentrations and fire possibility, with hazardous area-I up to 4 meters and hazardous area-II 4-8 meters in radius around the fuel dispensers.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	The study used standard methods for BTEX measurement, reducing detection bias. However, variations in sampling or analysis could introduce bias.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	The study did not mention any dropout or attrition of participants, reducing the risk of attrition bias.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	The study provided detailed methods and results, reducing the risk of reporting bias. However, selective reporting of outcomes could still be a potential bias.
Other bias	Low risk	Potential biases could include confounding factors not accounted for in the risk assessment, such as variations in environmental conditions or worker behavior.

Chen et al. 2020

Methods	<p>The study used a combination of field observations and chemical box modeling to assess the impacts of oil and natural gas (O&NG) exploration on tropospheric ozone (O₃) and regional air quality in the Yellow River delta (YelRD) region of northern China. Here is a breakdown of the method:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Participants: The study team conducted observations in the YelRD region, targeting areas affected by O&NG extraction activities. ● Intervention: Intensive field observations were conducted during two periods: February–March and June–July 2017. These observations aimed to measure concentrations of volatile organic compounds (VOCs), O₃, nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), carbon monoxide (CO), and other pollutants.
----------------	---

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Outcome: The field observations provided data on ambient VOC concentrations, O₃ levels, and other pollutants, which were used to analyze the impact of O&NG extraction on atmospheric chemistry.
Participants	<p>The study focused on the Yellow River delta (YeIRD) region in northern China, specifically targeting areas impacted by oil and natural gas (O&NG) extraction activities. The region includes several cities and has a population of 9.85 million. Field observations were conducted in this region during two periods: February–March and June–July 2017.</p>
Interventions	<p>The study involved intensive field observations to measure the concentrations of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and other atmospheric pollutants in the YeIRD region. Source samples were collected from oil and gas wells to obtain VOC source profiles. Chemical box modeling was used to analyze the impact of VOC emissions from oil fields on atmospheric chemistry and ozone (O₃) pollution in the region.</p>
Outcomes	<p>The study aimed to assess the impacts of O&NG exploration on tropospheric O₃ and regional air quality in China. It found very high concentrations of ambient VOCs in the region, with high-O₃ episodes frequently observed in summer but not encountered during wintertime. The chemical budgets of reactive oxygen species (ROx) radicals and O₃ were dissected, highlighting the significant role of VOCs, particularly oxygenated VOCs (OVOCs), in atmospheric oxidation capacity and O₃ formation. The study concluded that reducing NO_x emissions would be an effective way to control O₃ pollution in the YeIRD region.</p>
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	There may be a risk of detection bias in the study, particularly regarding the measurement of VOCs and other pollutants. The instruments used for monitoring these compounds need to be properly calibrated and sensitive to ensure accurate measurements.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	There is no clear indication of attrition bias in the study, as the methods and participants seem consistent throughout the observation periods.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Unclear risk	The study appears comprehensive in reporting its findings and methods.
Other bias	Unclear risk	The study's focus on a specific region and industry (O&NG extraction) may introduce bias in terms of generalizability to other regions or industries. Additionally, the study's reliance on modeling for some analyses could introduce bias if the model assumptions or parameters are not accurate.

Colborn et al 2014

Methods	Assessment of Air Quality in a Rural Western Colorado Area with Residential Proximity to Gas Wells Before, During, and After Hydraulic Fracturing
Participants	Air samples were collected in a rural area of western Colorado where residences and gas wells co-exist. The study area included a fixed sampling station near a well pad with 16 vertical gas wells.
Interventions	Air sampling was conducted weekly for one year, from July 2010 to October 2011, covering periods before, during, and after drilling and hydraulic fracturing of the gas wells.
Outcomes	The study assessed the levels of non-methane hydrocarbons (NMHCs), including selected polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), before, during, and after drilling and hydraulic fracturing. Methylene chloride, a toxic solvent not commonly reported in drilling or fracturing products, was also measured. Health effects of NMHCs and PAHs were reviewed from existing literature.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	The study might be prone to detection bias as it focused on specific chemicals (NMHCs, PAHs, methylene chloride) and did not consider a broader range of potential pollutants associated with drilling and fracturing activities.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	There is no information provided on attrition or loss of samples over the course of the study, which could introduce bias if there was differential loss of samples.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	The study appears to report all outcomes and findings, but there could be potential reporting bias if certain results were not included in the published report.
Other bias	Low risk	The study's reliance on existing literature for health effects of NMHCs and PAHs introduces the potential for bias if the literature review was not comprehensive or if there was selective reporting of health effects.

Elshaer et al 2022

Methods	This study utilized a cross-sectional comparative approach to assess oxidative stress in petroleum workers exposed to BTEX compounds. Forty workers exposed to BTEX and an equal number of non-exposed workers were included. Sociodemographic, occupational, and medical data were collected, along with measurements of BTEX exposure biomarkers in urine and serum concentrations of antioxidant trace metals. Activity of superoxide dismutase (SOD) and glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px) enzymes was also assessed.
----------------	---

Participants	The study was conducted in a petroleum refining company in Alexandria, Egypt. The study population comprised male petroleum workers with a service duration of five years or more in the company. Workers with certain exclusion criteria, such as history of contact with heavy metals or organic solvents, were excluded.
Interventions	The study did not involve an intervention but rather focused on observational data collection from BTEX-exposed and unexposed workers.
Outcomes	The main outcome measures included levels of BTEX exposure biomarkers, serum concentrations of antioxidant trace metals, and activity of SOD and GSH-Px enzymes.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	High risk	There is a potential risk of detection bias, as the measurement of biomarkers and enzyme activity may be influenced by the knowledge of workers' exposure status. However, efforts to blind laboratory personnel to the exposure status of participants could mitigate this bias.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	There is no mention of attrition in the study, which suggests a low risk of attrition bias.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	The study appears to report all relevant outcomes, indicating a low risk of reporting bias.
Other bias	Low risk	The study's selection criteria and methods for measuring exposures and outcomes are clearly described, which reduces the risk of other biases.

Geraldino et al 2021

Methods	Cross-sectional epidemiological study on gasoline station workers in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, focusing on toluene and xylene exposure.
Participants	275 gasoline station workers exposed mainly by inhalation (CSWs) and 100 office workers (OWs) as the comparison group.
Interventions	Collection and analysis of urine samples for biomarkers of toluene and xylene exposure (hippuric acid (HA) and methylhippuric acid (MHA)).
Outcomes	Workers exposed to fuels had higher levels of HA and MHA compared to the comparison group. Symptoms like altered mood/depression, cramps, dizziness, headaches, and others were more frequent in exposed workers.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

--	--	--

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	Low risk, as biomonitoring methods were likely standardized and applied consistently.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	High risk	Potential risk, as some samples were excluded from analysis due to creatinine levels outside the recommended range.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	Low risk, as the study appears to have reported all relevant findings without selectively excluding data.
Other bias	High risk	Potential risk, as the study did not specify details about potential confounding factors or control measures for other workplace exposures.

Gilman et al 2013

Methods	<p>The study measured a wide range of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) at the Boulder Atmospheric Observatory (BAO) in winter 2011 to analyze the composition and influence of VOC emissions from oil and natural gas (O&NG) operations in northeastern Colorado.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Measurement Locations: The study conducted wintertime measurements at NOAA's Boulder Atmospheric Observatory (BAO) in 2011. Two summertime studies were also conducted in northeastern Colorado, one in Boulder and another near Fort Collins. 2. Instrumentation: VOCs were measured in situ by a custom-built, two-channel gas chromatograph–mass spectrometer (GC-MS). The instrument collected ambient air samples and analyzed them for VOC content. 3. Comparison Sites: Ship-borne measurements in Houston, Texas, and measurements in Pasadena, California, were included for comparison.
Participants	The study did not involve human participants. It focused on measuring VOC concentrations in the atmosphere.
Interventions	There was no intervention in this study. It was observational, measuring VOC concentrations at different locations.
Outcomes	The study aimed to analyze the composition and influence of VOC emissions from oil and natural gas operations in northeastern Colorado, particularly focusing on differentiating between VOCs from O&NG operations and urban sources and estimating the reactivity of VOCs with the hydroxyl radical (OH).
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	The study used advanced instrumentation for VOC measurement, likely minimizing detection bias.

Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	Not applicable as there were no human participants or follow-up involved.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	The study appears to have reported all measured VOC concentrations and their reactivity accurately.
Other bias	Unclear risk	There might be potential bias related to the selection of measurement locations and the representativeness of the study area to draw broader conclusions about VOC emissions from O&NG operations in other regions. The study acknowledges these limitations.

Harati et al 2019

Methods	The study conducted a cross-sectional assessment of health risks related to exposure to volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and hydrogen sulfide (H ₂ S) in the petrochemical industry in Iran. Sampling and analysis were performed during winter 2016, with 123 samples collected from the ambient air. Three methods (numbers 1500, 1501, and 6013) from the National Institute of Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) were used for sampling and analysis of VOCs and H ₂ S. Risk assessment of chemical pollutants was conducted using a semi-quantitative method from the Occupational Safety and Health Division, Singapore. Cancer risk analysis was based on Chronic Daily Intake (CDI), and non-cancer risk was calculated using Exposure Concentration (EC).
Participants	The study included workers in the petrochemical industry in Iran who were exposed to VOCs and H ₂ S for more than 4 hours per day.
Interventions	Sampling and analysis of VOCs and H ₂ S were carried out using the NIOSH methods. Gas Chromatography-Flame Ionization Detector (GC-FID) was used for VOC analysis, while Ion Chromatography was used for H ₂ S analysis.
Outcomes	The study found that the average concentration of benzene in the breathing zone of workers exceeded the Threshold Limit Values-Time Weighted Average (TLV-TWA). Benzene was identified as posing the highest risk among the studied chemical substances. The mean cancer risk for workers exposed to benzene was estimated to be higher than the acceptable standard, indicating a potential for increased cancer risk. Non-cancer risk for BTX was also found to be higher than the acceptable standard.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	There may be a risk of detection bias in this study. The methods used for sampling and analysis may not have been sensitive enough to detect low levels of exposure, potentially leading to an underestimation of risks.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	Attrition bias could be present if there were missing data from the study

Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	There is a possibility of reporting bias in this study.
Other bias	High risk	Other biases could include confounding factors that were not accounted for in the analysis. Factors such as smoking, diet, and other occupational exposures could influence the results and introduce bias.

Harbi et al.2020

Methods	<p>Methods:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sample Collection and Analytical Methods: Air samples were collected at eight gasoline stations in Kuwait over two consecutive days during the summer. Sampling locations included the cashier office, pump area, and ambient atmosphere. BTEX compounds were collected using Summa-polished stainless steel canisters and Tedlar bags. Analysis was done using a thermal desorption system coupled with gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. ● Risk Assessment: The study assessed deterministic and stochastic exposure to BTEX compounds. Deterministic assessment estimated cancer risk (CR) and hazard risk (non-cancer risk) based on exposure concentrations and inhalation rates. Stochastic assessment used a Monte Carlo simulation to estimate risks to all workers in the gasoline stations.
Participants	The study included 80 male workers, 10 at each gasoline station, who were interviewed about their age, marital status, body mass index, length of service, and work schedule. They were also questioned about health symptoms experienced during their work shifts.
Interventions	The study did not include a specific intervention. Instead, it focused on assessing the current exposure levels and associated health risks to gasoline station workers
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The study found that gasoline station workers were exposed to high levels of BTEX compounds, exceeding NIOSH exposure limits. This exposure was associated with an elevated cancer risk, particularly for benzene and ethyl benzene. Workers reported symptoms such as headache, depression, fatigue, and throat irritation. ● Recommendations included improving ventilation systems, installing fans, or building gasoline stations in locations with good natural air exchange to reduce BTEX exposure.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	The study used reliable analytical methods and equipment for sampling and analysis, reducing the risk of detection bias.

Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	The study did not mention any attrition or dropout of participants, indicating a low risk of attrition bias.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	The study provided detailed methods and results, reducing the risk of reporting bias.
Other bias	Low risk	The study did not mention randomization or blinding procedures, which could introduce bias. However, since the study focused on observational data collection, these biases are less relevant.

Heibati et al 2017

Methods	Evaluation of Benzene, Toluene, Ethylbenzene, and Xylene (BTEX) Exposure Among Workers at Four Stations of a Major Oil Distribution Company in Iran
Participants	The study included 50 workers from various job roles (tanker loading workers, tank-gauging workers, drivers, firefighters, and office workers) at four stations of an oil distribution company in Northern Iran.
Interventions	Personal BTEX exposure samples were collected over an 8-hour working shift for each participant. The sampling was conducted in November 2016.
Outcomes	The study measured mean BTEX concentrations (benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylene) for workers across the four sites. The 8-hour averaged personal exposure benzene concentration exceeded the recommended value established by the Iranian Committee for Review and Collection of Occupational Exposure Limit and American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists. The study also calculated excess lifetime cancer risk for exposure to benzene across workers at each site. Risk management approaches to reducing exposures to BTEX compounds, especially benzene, were recommended.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	High risk	There may be a risk of detection bias as the exposure measurements were collected using personal samplers, which might not capture all aspects of exposure variability.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	There is no mention of attrition in the study, so attrition bias is unlikely to be a significant concern.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	The study provides detailed methods and results, reducing the risk of reporting bias. However, selective reporting of results could be a potential concern.
Other bias	Low risk	The study did not mention blinding or randomization, which could introduce bias. Additionally, the study's small sample size and single-point measurement may limit the generalizability of the results.

Heibati et al 2018

Methods	The study aimed to evaluate the exposure of workers at four stations of a major oil distribution company in Iran to benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylene (BTEX). Personal exposure samples were collected over an 8-hour working shift for 50 workers at each station. Sampling was conducted using Radiello® Passive monitors worn in the respiratory zone while workers performed their usual activities. Samples were analyzed using gas chromatography with a flame ionizing detector.
Participants	The study included 50 workers at each of the four stations, including tanker loading workers, tank-gauging workers, drivers, firefighters, and office workers.
Interventions	Personal exposure measurements were taken over the course of an 8-hour working shift using passive monitors worn by the workers. Samples were collected and analyzed for BTEX compounds.
Outcomes	The study found that the mean concentrations of benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylene varied across the four stations. Benzene and toluene concentrations exceeded recommended values at some stations. Tanker loading was identified as the highest risk occupation, and benzene was identified as the strongest contributor to risk among the BTEX compounds.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	There may be a risk of detection bias in this study. The passive monitors used may not have been sensitive enough to detect low levels of exposure, potentially leading to an underestimation of risks.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	Attrition bias could be present if there were missing data or dropouts from the study.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	There is a possibility of reporting bias in this study. If the researchers selectively reported results that supported their hypothesis, it could lead to an overestimation or underestimation of risks.
Other bias	Low risk	Other biases could include confounding factors that were not accounted for in the analysis. Factors such as smoking, diet, and other occupational exposures could influence the results and introduce bias. Additionally, the study's design as a cross-sectional study may limit the ability to establish causality between exposure and health outcomes.

Jalilian et al. 2022

Methods	To investigate the impact of BTEX compounds on blood and spirometry parameters of staff in the Abadan petroleum refinery, Iran. Air sampling for BTEX compounds followed NIOSH method 1,501. Blood parameters were analyzed using an automated hematology analyzer, and spirometry parameters were assessed using a Micro Direct automated spirometer. SPSS 20 software was used for data analysis.
Participants	The study included 80 male staff members from the Abadan petroleum refinery in Iran. 40 participants were exposed to BTEX compounds, while 40 were non-exposed. All participants had no history of smoking, acute illness, systemic disease, or family malignancy history.
Interventions	Air sampling for BTEX compounds was conducted using the NIOSH method 1,501. Blood parameters were analyzed using an automated hematology analyzer, and spirometry parameters were assessed using a Micro Direct automated spirometer. Data analysis was performed using SPSS 20 software.
Outcomes	The study aimed to investigate the impact of BTEX compounds on blood and spirometry parameters. Results showed that while total BTEX concentrations were generally within recommended limits, benzene concentrations exceeded the allowable limit. However, there was no statistically significant difference in blood and spirometry parameters between the exposed and non-exposed groups.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	Low risk, as standardized methods were used for air sampling and laboratory analyses.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	Low risk, as all 80 participants completed the study.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	Low risk, as the study appears to have reported all measured outcomes without selectively reporting results.
Other bias	Unclear risk	Potential sources of bias include uncontrolled confounding factors, such as other occupational exposures or lifestyle factors. The reliance on self-reported information for medical history could introduce recall bias. Additionally, the study's focus on male workers limits its generalizability to female workers.

Jalilian et al 2022

Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Study Design: This was a cross-sectional, descriptive, and analytical study. ● Participants: The study involved employees of Abadan Oil Refining Company, Iran, with at least one year of experience. ● Intervention: Air sampling and BTEX analysis were conducted according to NIOSH method number 1501. ● Outcome Measures: The study aimed to identify the highest occupational exposure levels to benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylene (BTEX) in Abadan Oil Refining Company, Iran, in 2020. ● Data Analysis: SPSS 20 software was used for data analysis.
Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Employees of Abadan Oil Refining Company, Iran, with at least one year of experience. ● Air samples were collected from 40 workers, with two samples taken from each worker.
Interventions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Air sampling and BTEX analysis were conducted using activated charcoal and a low flow rate SKC pump according to NIOSH method No. 1501. ● The method proposed by the Department of Occupational Safety and Health of Malaysia was used to determine the risk of exposure to BTEX pollutants.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The results showed that employees were exposed to BTEX pollutants during their work. ● Benzene had the highest risk ranking in seven operating units and a low risk ranking in three other units. ● Toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylene had very low risks in all operating units.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	The study used standardized methods for air sampling and analysis, which reduces the risk of detection bias
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	The study does not mention any loss of participants or missing data, which reduces the risk of attrition bias.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	The study provides detailed methods and results, reducing the risk of reporting bias.
Other bias	Low risk	The study does not mention any specific measures taken to address potential biases related to participant selection or data analysis, which could be a limitation.

Khoshakhlagh et al 2023

Methods	The study employed a cross-sectional design, collecting air samples from workers' breathing zones. BTEX concentrations were measured using the NIOSH 1501 method. The samples were collected during winter and summer of the year 2021. The health risk assessment was performed using USEPA methods for carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic risks.
Participants	The study included employees of the oil refinery, specifically those working in catalytic reforming unit, kerosene transportation area, new transportation area, gasoline post-treatment unit, alkylation unit, wastewater treatment plant, and distillation units.
Interventions	There was no specific intervention in this study; it was observational in nature, focusing on measuring BTEX concentrations and assessing health risks.
Outcomes	The study found that BTEX concentrations were higher in the summer than in the winter season for all workstations, especially for toluene and ethylbenzene. The mean values of exposure to benzene for repairmen and site men were higher than the threshold limit value for both seasons. Non-carcinogenic risk values exceeded acceptable levels for several compounds in both seasons, and definite carcinogenic risk was indicated for benzene and ethylbenzene exposure in all workstations in both seasons.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	There is a low risk of detection bias as BTEX concentrations were measured using standardized methods (NIOSH 1501 method) for all participants.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	There is a low risk of attrition bias as all participants included in the study were analyzed, and there is no mention of dropout rates or missing data.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	There is a low risk of reporting bias as the study reports all outcomes and findings as measured, without selective reporting.
Other bias	Unclear risk	There might be a potential bias due to the sampling method, as samples were collected from workers' breathing zones, which might not represent the overall exposure in the workplace. Additionally, the study did not mention whether the researchers were blinded to the exposure status of the participants, which could introduce bias.

Kitwattanavong et al. 2013

Methods	The study aimed to estimate the occupational health risk of petrol station workers in the inner city of Bangkok from exposure to BTEX (benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylene) and carbonyl compounds (formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, and propionaldehyde) via inhalation.
Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of Participants: The study included 36 samples collected from two petrol station workers at each station, representing their personal exposure, and one sample from the ambient air inside the station complex. ● Selection Criteria: Petrol station workers were selected randomly, excluding those who smoked to avoid additional sources of exposure.
Interventions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sampling Procedure: Ambient air sampling was performed using a sampling train of DNPH cartridges and charcoal glass tubes connected to a low-flow personal air pump during an 8-hour working period. Personal exposure sampling was conducted using the same system clipped to the workers' breathing zone. ● Data Collection: Questionnaires were used to collect general information and factors for calculating exposure, such as body weight, age, activities, and health status.
Outcomes	Risk Assessment: The levels of benzene, ethylbenzene, formaldehyde, and acetaldehyde were used to assess the lifetime cancer risk, which was found to be higher than acceptable criteria. However, non-cancer health risks from toluene, m/p-xylene, o-xylene, and propionaldehyde were within acceptable levels.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	The study utilized quantitative analytical methods (GC/FID and HPLC/UV) to measure BTEX and carbonyl compounds, reducing the risk of detection bias.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	There is no information provided regarding attrition or dropout rates in the study.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	The study provides detailed information on the methods, participants, interventions, and outcomes, reducing the risk of reporting bias.
Other bias	Low risk	The study conducted personal sampling within the workers' breathing zone, which may better represent their actual exposure compared to ambient air sampling alone, reducing potential bias

Kumari et al 2023

Methods	The study aimed to estimate the health risk for workers due to exposure to BTEX compounds after the implementation of vapour recovery systems (VRS) at fuel stations. Air samples were collected using sorbent tubes and analyzed using gas chromatography.
Participants	The participants were fuel station workers exposed to BTEX compounds during their work.
Interventions	The intervention was the implementation of vapour recovery systems (VRS) at the fuel stations to reduce the emission of BTEX compounds.
Outcomes	The outcome of interest was the health risk assessment, including cancer risk (CR) and hazard quotient (HQ), based on the concentrations of BTEX compounds in the air samples.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	The study used NIOSH methods for sampling and gas chromatography for analysis, which are standard techniques. However, there could be bias if the sampling or analysis was not conducted properly or if there were errors in calibration or data recording.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	There is no mention of attrition in the study, as it likely did not involve longitudinal follow-up or loss of participants.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	The study reports detailed methods, results, and conclusions, which reduces the risk of reporting bias. However, the study could be susceptible to publication bias if only significant results were reported.
Other bias	Low risk	Other potential biases include the representativeness of the study sample, the generalizability of the findings to other fuel stations or settings, and the potential influence of confounding variables such as other sources of VOCs or occupational exposures.

Matatiele et al 2020

Methods	Biomonitoring study conducted on 29 petroleum refinery workers in South Africa from 2010 to 2013.
Participants	29 refinery workers
Interventions	Urine samples were collected post-shift and analyzed for biomarkers of exposure to benzene, toluene, and xylene using high-performance liquid chromatography and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry.

Outcomes	Most workers had exposure levels within recommended limits, but some were overexposed to toluene. Exposure levels varied over the four-year period.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	Low risk, as biomonitoring methods were likely standardized and applied consistently.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	Low risk, as the study appears to have maintained a relatively stable participant group over the four-year period.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	Low risk, as the study seems to have reported all relevant findings without selectively excluding data.
Other bias	High risk	Potential risk, as the study did not specify details about potential confounding factors or control measures for other workplace exposures.

Mckenzie et al 2012

Methods	Health Impact Assessment of Air Emissions from Natural Gas Development in Garfield County, Colorado
Participants	The study focused on two populations: residents living more than half a mile from wells and residents living within half a mile from wells in Garfield County, Colorado.
Interventions	The study estimated chronic and subchronic non-cancer hazard indices (HIs) and cancer risks from exposure to hydrocarbons using EPA guidance.
Outcomes	The study assessed the health risks associated with exposure to air emissions from natural gas development, particularly focusing on residents' proximity to wells. It estimated the potential health effects of exposure to hydrocarbons, including benzene, trimethylbenzenes, xylenes, and aliphatic hydrocarbons.
Notes	The study suggests that residents living in closer proximity to natural gas wells may face greater health risks from air emissions associated with natural gas development.

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	High risk	There is a potential for detection bias as the study focused on specific pollutants and exposure scenarios, which may not capture the full range of potential health impacts associated with natural gas development.

Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	There is no information provided on attrition or loss of samples over the course of the study, which could introduce bias if there was differential loss of samples.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	The study appears to report all outcomes and findings, but there could be potential reporting bias if certain results were not included in the published report.
Other bias	Low risk	The study's reliance on EPA methodology and existing air toxics data introduces the potential for bias if the methodology or data collection methods were not robust or comprehensive.

Mirrezai et al 2020

Methods	The study used the AERMOD dispersion model coupled with the WRF model to predict ground-level concentrations of benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylenes (BTEX) emitted from gas flares. The accuracy of the dispersion model was verified using measured ambient SO ₂ data. Health risk assessment was conducted based on the OEHHA guidelines for acute and chronic non-cancerous and cancerous risks.
Participants	The study area included residential areas, industrial areas (refinery sites), two cities (Asalouyeh and Nakhil Taghi), and camps for workers near gas refinery plants.
Interventions	The study did not involve any specific intervention but focused on assessing the health risks associated with BTEX emissions from gas flares.
Outcomes	The study found that the chronic non-carcinogenic risk of BTEX emitted from gas flares was within acceptable limits in residential areas and most refinery sites. However, the acute non-carcinogenic risk was higher in refinery sites and lower in other areas. The carcinogenic risk of benzene and ethylbenzene exceeded the acceptable limit in refinery sites and two cities but was within limits in nearby camps.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	High risk	There is a potential for detection bias as the study relied on predicted concentrations of BTEX from the AERMOD model, which may not perfectly reflect actual exposure levels.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	There is no indication of attrition bias in this study.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	Reporting bias is possible if there was selective reporting of results based on the outcomes observed.
Other bias	Low risk	Other biases could include model assumptions and limitations, as well as the representativeness of the sampling locations for BTEX and SO ₂ .

Molaei et al 2020

Methods	The study aimed to evaluate the health risk associated with exposure to heavy metals (iron, zinc, cadmium, arsenic, nickel, lead, and mercury), benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylene (BTEX), and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in a secondary oil re-refining factory. It was a descriptive, cross-sectional study conducted at eight sampling points within the factory. Air samples were collected and analyzed using the NIOSH 1501 method to determine the concentrations of BTEX, 16 Σ PAHs, and heavy metals. The risk assessment of these contaminants was conducted using the RAIS software, and the risk of non-carcinogenic compounds was estimated based on the reference respiratory concentration.
Participants	workers in the secondary oil re-refining factory
Interventions	Air sampling and analysis for heavy metals, BTEX, and PAHs
Outcomes	Evaluation of health risks associated with exposure to the above contaminants
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Unclear risk	Low, as the NIOSH 1501 method is a standardized procedure for air sampling and analysis.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	Not applicable, as there is no mention of participant attrition.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	Low, as the study provides detailed information on the methods, results, and conclusions.
Other bias	Unclear risk	Possible bias related to the selection of sampling points or the representativeness of the study area, but this is not explicitly addressed in the provided information.

Moolla et al 2015

Methods	The study monitored BTEX concentrations at a diesel refueling bay in Johannesburg, South Africa, using gas chromatography coupled with a photo-ionization detector.
Participants	The participants were likely workers at the diesel refueling bay, potentially including pump attendants and other staff members.
Interventions	The study did not involve an intervention but focused on monitoring BTEX concentrations in the air at the refueling bay.
Outcomes	The study aimed to evaluate whether BTEX concentrations at the refueling bay exceeded legal standards, both national and international, and to investigate the variation of BTEX values during a typical day on site.

Notes	
--------------	--

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	There might be a risk of detection bias if the monitoring equipment was not calibrated correctly or if there were issues with the sampling methodology. However, since gas chromatography is a standard method for BTEX analysis, this risk is likely low.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	There should be no attrition bias in this study since it involves monitoring environmental data and does not involve participant follow-up or dropout.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	Reporting bias could be a concern if the researchers selectively reported results that favored a particular outcome. However, without access to the full study, it's challenging to assess this bias.
Other bias	Low risk	Other biases, such as selection bias or confounding factors, could affect the study's results. For example, if the sampling location was not representative of typical exposure scenarios, the results might not accurately reflect the true exposure levels.

Moridzadeh et al 2020

Methods	This cross-sectional study aimed to assess urinary levels of benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylenes (BTEX) among workers in the South Pars Gas Field (SPGF) in Assaluyeh, Iran. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC/MS) was used to analyze BTEX levels in urine samples collected from 40 workers (case group) and 31 administrative employees (control group). Pre-shift and post-shift urine samples were collected from the case group, while the control group provided mid-morning urine samples.
Participants	The case group consisted of workers exposed to BTEX compounds in the outdoor and indoor environment, while the control group comprised administrative staff located away from the exposure sources. The study excluded individuals expected to be exposed to BTEX from other sources.
Interventions	Urine samples were collected from the case group twice a day during the work shift (pre-shift and post-shift), while the control group provided one mid-morning urine sample. Samples were stored at -20°C for analysis.
Outcomes	The study measured urinary concentrations of benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, m,p-xylene, and o-xylene. Significant differences were observed in urinary BTEX levels between smokers and non-smokers in both groups.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	Low risk, as GC/MS is a reliable method for detecting BTEX compounds in urine.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	Low risk, as all recruited participants provided urine samples as per the study protocol.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	Low risk, as the study appears to have reported all measured outcomes without selective reporting.
Other bias	Low risk	Potential sources of bias could include unmeasured confounders related to exposure levels or lifestyle factors that may affect BTEX concentrations.

Mousavie et al 2019

Methods	The study used a cross-sectional design to assess neurobehavioral symptoms in operational workers exposed to BTEX compounds in an oil refinery. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● BTEX compounds were sampled using NIOSH method 1501. ● Sampling was conducted using activated carbon adsorbent tubes containing coconut shell charcoal. ● Sampling duration: 45 minutes to eight hours. ● Flow rate: 0.2 liters per minute.
Participants	The study included 78 operational workers (exposure group) and 85 administrative staff (control group) from an oil refinery in southern Iran in 2018. Participants had over five years of work experience, no history of neurological diseases, and did not use psychiatric drugs or alcohol.
Interventions	BTEX compounds were sampled using NIOSH method 1501 with activated carbon adsorbent tubes containing coconut shell charcoal. Sampling was conducted at a flow rate of 0.2 liters per minute for 45 minutes to eight hours.
Outcomes	Neurobehavioral symptoms were assessed using the Swedish Q16 questionnaire for long-term solvent-exposed workers, with a focus on benzene, toluene, ethyl benzene, and xylene (BTEX) exposure. Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 22 software.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	There may be a risk of detection bias as the exposure group was aware of their exposure status, which could influence their reporting of symptoms compared to the control group.

Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	High risk	The study excluded individuals with certain criteria, potentially introducing bias if these exclusions were not random.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	The use of self-reported questionnaires for symptom assessment could introduce reporting bias, as participants might underreport or overreport symptoms.
Other bias	High risk	The study did not mention randomization or blinding procedures, which could introduce bias in participant selection and outcome assessment.

Partovi et al 2018

Methods	This study conducted a comprehensive risk assessment of exposure to BTEX compounds in the National Company for Distribution of Petroleum Products in Iran. Sampling was carried out in different parts of the company using activated carbon, and Gas Chromatography-Flame Ionization Detector (GC-FID) was used for analysis. Lifetime cancer risk (LCR) was calculated for carcinogenic risk assessment, while hazard quotient (HQ) was calculated for non-carcinogenic risk assessment.
Participants	The study involved individuals in charge of different parts of the company, and data were collected through measurement. A total of 40 exposed workers and 40 unexposed workers were included in the study.
Interventions	There was no intervention involved in this study; it focused on observational data collection and risk assessment.
Outcomes	The study assessed the carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic risk of exposure to BTEX compounds in different parts of the company. Results indicated definite, probable, and possible risks in various units.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	There is a potential risk of detection bias, as the measurement of BTEX concentrations may be influenced by knowledge of the workers' exposure status. Efforts to blind laboratory personnel could mitigate this bias.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	There is no mention of attrition in the study, suggesting a low risk of attrition bias.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	The study appears to report all relevant outcomes, indicating a low risk of reporting bias.
Other bias	Low risk	The study's methods for sampling, analysis, and risk assessment are clearly described, reducing the risk of other biases.

Ramirez et al 2012

Methods	The study aimed to characterize the risk of exposure to volatile organic compounds (VOCs) through inhalation in individuals living near the largest chemical production site in the Mediterranean area
Participants	The study included individuals living in the vicinity of the chemical production site in the Mediterranean area.
Interventions	The intervention was the monitoring campaign conducted over 276 days in three different locations around the chemical site. Air samples were collected using two methods: (1) active sampling of air for 24 hours in charcoal tubes followed by extraction with carbon disulphide and GC-MS analysis (method A), and (2) thermal desorption method based on standard method EN 14662-1 for 2-hour samples over eight days at each site during the first period of sampling (method B).
Outcomes	The study quantified 44 VOCs with toxicological data available concerning their carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic health effects. The average concentrations of VOCs were compared to their chronic reference concentrations to determine non-carcinogenic health effects. The global average cancer risk due to VOC exposure in the area was calculated.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	The study used standard methods for VOC detection, minimizing detection bias.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Unclear risk	There is no indication of attrition bias as all samples were analyzed.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Unclear risk	The study appears to report all findings without selective reporting.
Other bias	Unclear risk	The study acknowledges limitations and uncertainties associated with risk estimates, which could introduce bias

Ridderseth et al 2022

Methods	The study aimed to assess the time trend of full-shift benzene exposure from 2002 to 2018 among workers in the Norwegian petroleum offshore industry. A total of 924 measurements of benzene exposure were included, with a median sampling duration of 680 minutes. The study used multilevel mixed-effects tobit regression analyses to estimate the overall geometric mean (GM) and 95% confidence interval, time trends, and determinants of exposure.
Participants	The study included workers from various job groups, including laboratory technicians, mechanics, process operators, and industrial cleaners, in the Norwegian petroleum offshore industry.

Interventions	The study did not involve any intervention but focused on assessing benzene exposure levels among workers over time and identifying possible determinants of exposure.
Outcomes	The main outcome of the study was the assessment of benzene exposure levels among different job groups over time, as well as the identification of factors influencing exposure levels, such as job group, design of process area, season, and wind speed.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	There may be a risk of detection bias due to the variability in measurement methods and instruments used to assess benzene exposure over the study period. However, efforts were made to standardize measurement protocols within the industry.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	There is a potential for attrition bias, as the study included measurements from different time periods, and not all installations were represented in each period. However, this was addressed by analyzing time trends within each period and adjusting for relevant factors.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	There is a risk of reporting bias, as not all measurements may have been included in the study, particularly if they were not reported in the available reports or database. However, efforts were made to include all relevant measurements in the analysis.
Other bias	Low risk	Other potential sources of bias include confounding factors that were not accounted for in the analysis, such as changes in work practices or environmental conditions that could affect benzene exposure levels. Efforts were made to adjust for known determinants of exposure, but there may still be uncontrolled factors influencing the results.

Thekathuek et al 2023

Methods	The study assessed the risk of benzene exposure to the nervous system in gas station operators. Data were collected from 100 fuel service personnel working at fuel dispensers and 100 employees working outside fuel dispensers. Demographic information, work history, symptoms of nervous system disorders, and t,t-muconic acid in urine were collected using interview questionnaires and urine sample analysis. The risk assessment included hazard identification, health effect assessment, and exposure assessment.
Participants	The study population consisted of employees of gas stations in Rayong province, Thailand. The inclusion criteria included fuel service station employees aged between 18 and 60 years, able to read, listen, and write Thai, consent to participate in the research, and able to work on the data collection

	day for 8 hours.
Interventions	The intervention involved collecting data through interview questionnaires and urine sample collection. Hazard identification, health effect assessment, and exposure assessment were conducted to assess benzene exposure risk.
Outcomes	The study found a statistically significant relationship between t,t-muconic acid concentrations and neurological disorders. Most risks were at a low level, suggesting a low risk of benzene exposure on the nervous system. The benzene neurotoxic risk assessment model was considered useful for implementation, but further studies with larger samples are recommended.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	High risk	There might be detection bias in the assessment of neurological symptoms, as the symptoms were self-reported, which could be influenced by the participants' knowledge of their exposure status.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	Attrition bias could occur if there were missing data or if participants dropped out of the study. The study did not mention how missing data or dropout rates were handled, which could introduce bias.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	Reporting bias could occur if there were selective reporting of outcomes. The study did not provide information on whether all collected outcomes were reported, which could introduce bias.
Other bias	Low risk	Other potential sources of bias include selection bias, as the sample was selected using cluster random sampling, which may not represent the entire population of gas station workers. Additionally, information bias could occur if there were errors in data collection or measurement of t,t-muconic acid levels.

Tong et al 2020

Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sampling Methods: VOCs samples were collected from July 7–12, 2014, at 10 working sites covering 5 key production areas of the refinery. Sampling was conducted according to GBZ159-2004 regulations for workplace air sampling. ● Analysis: Nine VOCs were selected for analysis, including benzene, toluene, xylene, ethyl benzene, n-hexane, cyclohexane, heptane, hexane, and pentane. Samples were collected using a Gilair-3 air sampler and analyzed using gas chromatography. ● Risk Assessment: The study used probabilistic risk assessment methods, including an inhalation risk model and Monte Carlo simulation, to assess carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic risks. Sensitivity and uncertainty analysis were also conducted.
----------------	--

Participants	The study did not involve human participants directly but focused on evaluating the occupational health risks for workers in the petrochemical refinery.
Interventions	The study did not involve any specific intervention but aimed to assess the health risks associated with VOCs exposure in the refinery.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The results indicated that benzene, toluene, ethyl benzene, and xylene were the primary pollutants in the production areas, with the AHED and XFD areas being the main contributors. ● In terms of non-carcinogenic risk, the largest hazard index existed in the AHED area, but all production areas had non-carcinogenic risk values not exceeding 1. ● For carcinogenic risk, benzene and ethyl benzene posed the highest risks, with the AHED, DATA, and XFD areas showing relatively high carcinogenic risks.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	The study used standardized sampling and analysis methods to minimize detection bias. However, the possibility of bias due to equipment limitations or sampling errors cannot be entirely ruled out.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	Since the study did not involve human participants, attrition bias is not applicable.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	The study appears to provide a comprehensive report on the methods, results, and analysis, reducing the risk of reporting bias.
Other bias	Low risk	Other potential biases could include sampling site selection bias or variations in sampling conditions. However, the study attempts to mitigate these biases by selecting sites that represent key production areas and maintaining consistent sampling conditions.

Tunsaringkarn et al 2012

Methods	The study you described aimed to evaluate the exposure of gasoline station workers to benzene, formaldehyde, and acetaldehyde, which are carcinogenic substances commonly found in gasoline station environments. Inhalation and ambient air concentrations of benzene, formaldehyde, and acetaldehyde were measured using GC/FID and HPLC/UV detectors. Urinary biomarkers (t,t-MA, formaldehyde, and acetaldehyde) were analyzed using GC/FID.
Participants	<p>38 gasoline station workers from 6 gasoline stations in Pathumwan District, Bangkok, Thailand.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Healthy individuals with more than six months of work experience at their

	respective gasoline stations.
Interventions	Workers were provided with personal protective equipment (PPE) in the form of masks and were instructed to practice hand washing during their work shifts.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The average inhalation exposure concentrations of benzene, formaldehyde, and acetaldehyde were 195.56, 12.60, and 5.74 µg/m³, respectively. ● Lifetime cancer risk values for benzene, formaldehyde, and acetaldehyde were determined. ● After the intervention, urinary biomarkers showed a decrease in formaldehyde and acetaldehyde concentrations compared to before the intervention.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	The methods used for exposure assessment (GC/FID, HPLC/UV) are standard and unlikely to introduce bias.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	No information provided about the completeness of data collection or any missing data, which could introduce bias.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	The study appears to report all relevant outcomes without selective reporting.
Other bias	Low risk	The study does not mention any other potential sources of bias, such as confounding variables or funding sources.

Yousefi et al 2022

Methods	The objective of this study was to measure the concentrations of benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylene (BTEX) compounds at 13 gas stations in Mashhad, Iran, during autumn 2018. Gas samples were collected using charcoal sorbent tubes and an SKC pump, and analysis was performed using gas chromatography with flame ionization detection.
Participants	The study included a total of 39 samples collected from 13 gas stations in Mashhad, Iran.
Interventions	Sampling was conducted at these gas stations in autumn 2018 in three working shifts (morning, noon, and night) using the NIOSH-1501 method, which involves using charcoal sorbent tubes and an SKC pump with a flow rate of 0.2 L/min for sampling the BTEX compounds.
Outcomes	The concentrations of benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylene in the air of the gas stations were measured. The mean and standard deviation of these concentrations were calculated, and the relationship between BTEX compounds and meteorological parameters was assessed.

Notes	
--------------	--

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	There is a potential risk of detection bias in this study, as the method used for sampling and analyzing the BTEX compounds could introduce variability in the measurements. However, efforts were made to minimize this bias through calibration of the sampling pump and the use of standard procedures for sample analysis.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	There is no indication of attrition bias in this study, as all collected samples were included in the analysis.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	There is a potential risk of reporting bias, as the study only reports the concentrations of BTEX compounds and their relationship with meteorological parameters. Other potential confounding factors or sources of bias are not addressed in the study.
Other bias	Low risk	The study does not provide information on potential sources of bias related to the selection of gas stations or the sampling process. Further information on the representativeness of the sample and the generalizability of the findings would help assess the risk of bias in this study.

Zhang et al 2021

Methods	The study aimed to determine the association between exposure to benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, xylene, and styrene (BTEXS) and lung function decline in petrochemical workers in southern China. A total of 635 workers from a petrochemical plant with valid lung function tests were included. Generalized linear regression models and generalized weighted quantile sum (gWQS) regression models were used to estimate associations of individual BTEXS homologs and mixtures with lung function parameters and ventilation dysfunction risk. The gWQS index was used to quantify the weighted quartiles for BTEXS homologs. The study also explored the modification effect of smoking status, gender, and body mass index (BMI).
Participants	The study included 635 petrochemical workers from a plant in southern China with valid lung function tests.
Interventions	Lung function tests were conducted on the participants, and exposure to BTEXS compounds was assessed based on their work environment.
Outcomes	The study found a significant association between exposure to BTEXS compounds and decline in forced vital capacity percent predicted (FVC% of predicted) and an increased risk of lung ventilation dysfunction (LVD). The gWQS index was inversely associated with FVC% of predicted, vital capacity percent predicted (VC% of predicted), and forced expiratory volume in 1 second percent predicted (FEV1% predicted). The index was also significantly

	associated with overall LVD and its subtypes: mixed ventilation dysfunction (MVD) and restrictive ventilation dysfunction (RVD). Xylene, benzene, and toluene were identified as the priority pollutants in the BTEXS mixed exposure.
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	There may be a risk of detection bias, as the methods used for assessing lung function and BTEXS exposure may not have been sensitive enough to detect subtle changes or low levels of exposure, potentially leading to an underestimation of risks.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	Attrition bias could be present if there were missing data from the study.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	There is a possibility of reporting bias, as the researchers may have selectively reported results that supported their hypothesis
Other bias	Low risk	Other biases could include confounding factors that were not accounted for in the analysis. Factors such as other occupational exposures, lifestyle factors, or underlying health conditions could influence the results and introduce bias.

Zheng et al 2018

Methods	The study aimed to assess the levels, compositions, and sources of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) in an oil and gas station in northwest China over a year-long period. It utilized an online monitoring system to measure 57 VOCs designated as photochemical precursors.
Participants	The study did not involve human participants. It focused on monitoring VOC emissions at an oil and gas station in northwest China.
Interventions	There was no intervention in this observational study. The researchers continuously monitored VOC levels using an online monitoring system.
Outcomes	The study aimed to understand the VOC levels, compositions, and sources in an oil and gas station. It analyzed the concentrations of total VOCs, identified the main contributors, assessed the ozone formation potential, and determined the contributions of different sources to the total VOC emissions.
Notes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The average concentration of total VOCs was 297 ± 372 ppbv, with alkanes being the main contributor, accounting for 87.5% of total VOCs. ● Alkanes were identified as the most important VOC group for ozone formation potential. ● The main sources of VOCs were natural gas (62.6%), fuel evaporation (21.5%), combustion sources (10.9%), oil refining processes (3.8%), and asphalt (1.3%). ● The study found different diurnal patterns for the identified VOC sources, which were influenced by emission patterns and meteorological parameters.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The geographic origins of the five identified VOC sources were similar, with variations in seasonal contributions
--	---

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Low risk	The study used an online monitoring system with continuous measurement of VOCs, which reduces the risk of detection bias.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	There is no evidence of attrition bias as the study did not involve human participants or longitudinal follow-up.
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	The study appears to report all measured VOC concentrations and sources without selective reporting, reducing the risk of reporting bias.
Other bias	Unclear risk	The study does not mention any specific methods to address confounding factors or potential biases related to the measurement and analysis of VOCs. However, the use of standard calibration procedures and verification methods for the monitoring equipment helps minimize measurement bias.

Footnotes